

Competency-Based Management In Brazilian Federal Universities In The Context Of The National Policy For Employee Development

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EN Abstract. This research aims to broaden our understanding of the policies and practices aimed at the development of the federal civil servants in Brazil, considering the reference to the 2006, 2019 and 2020 Federal Decrees, based on the People Development Plans of the Brazilian Federal Universities. A thematic analysis of 23 plans was carried out, considering Competency-Based Management (CBM). The study indicates that the universities have adopted practices that converge with the Federal Decrees, using diverse and creative processes in the face of a lack of standardization of the plans, practices aimed at training rather than competencies, a lack of metrics for measuring the efficiency of the plans and technical and political challenges faced by the people management units.

Keywords: Public Policy; Public Management; Public Administration; Public official.

ES **Gestión de competencias en las Universidades Federales Brasileñas en el contexto de la Política Nacional de Desarrollo de los Empleados**

ES Resumen. Esta investigación tiene como objetivo ampliar la comprensión de las políticas y prácticas dirigidas al desarrollo de los servidores públicos federales en Brasil, considerando la referencia a los Decretos Federales de 2006, 2019 y 2020, a partir de los Planes de Desarrollo de Personas de las Universidades Federales Brasileñas. Se realizó un análisis temático de 23 planes, considerando la Gestión por Competencias. El estudio indica que las universidades han adoptado prácticas convergentes con los decretos, utilizando procesos diversos y creativos frente a la falta de estandarización de los planes, prácticas dirigidas a la formación y no a las competencias, falta de métricas para medir la eficiencia de los planes y desafíos técnicos y políticos enfrentados por las unidades de gestión de personas.

Palabras-clave: Políticas Públicas; Gestión Pública; Administración Pública; Servidores Públicos.

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1. Introduction

Public administration is the process of managing public affairs (Bergue, 2014), represented by an environment of interdisciplinary knowledge guided by converging values in pursuit of the public good (Marshall, 1998). According to Fevorini, Silva and Crepaldi (2014), since the end of the 1980s there has been a growing trend in the public sector towards adopting management processes supported by private sector practices and policies.

Fonseca et al. (2013) point out that the administrative reforms in Brazil are inspired by the New Public Management (NPM) (Sano & Abrucio, 2008), centered on a managerial conception that favors the dynamics of private initiative and market functioning and is focused on results, overcoming the bureaucratic model. Dalmau et al. (2022), considering the ongoing reforms, recognize important challenges for managers in the face of globalization, competitiveness and digital transformation, which demand constant reflection on ways of managing from a quality perspective, considering efficiency, efficacy and effectiveness centered on the citizen.

In the 1980s, public administration experienced a crisis (Gaetani, 1999), the consequences of which gave rise to the transition to state reform and social and democratic debates that consolidated the promulgation of the 1988 Federal Constitution (Andion, 2012). Article 37 of the 1988 Federal Constitution requires the public administration to pay attention to the principles of legality, impersonality, morality, publicity and efficiency. In this context, Dalmau et al. (2022) add that a new phase of public administration is emerging, challenging the paternalistic and bureaucratic approaches in defense of managerialism. This shift, which began in the 1990s, incorporated private sector practices based on strategic management models, consolidating Competency-Based Management as a central element in people development.

Thus, the field of management in general, and the area of people management in particular, in this context, are triggered by the process of globalization, which imposes important political, social and technological changes of a reformist nature, deepen challenges for public organizations (Sousa & Barbosa, 2018). They involve economic uncertainties in a context of competition, which makes the term 'competencies' more relevant in the context of public administration, with a view to promoting knowledge, skills and attitudes for working in complex environments (Nicolazzi, 2013).

In this effort, Competency-Based Management is designed in opposition to traditional models, due to the demands of organizations in the face of transformations in society (Dutra, 2008, 2009), with an emphasis on the effectiveness of people management (Morcerf et al., 2011), also recognized as an innovation in the context of public administration, as suggested by Montezano et al. (2019). Furthermore, it is considered an approach that requires further studies and research in public institutions (Vargas & Cagol, 2012; Silva, Cavalcante, Silva & Silva, 2021).

The competency-based model integrates processes such as admission, task allocation, performance evaluation, and personnel movement, aligning them with organizational competencies (Lima, 2005), in convergence with the demands of contemporary organizations (Bergue, 2011), aimed at the relationship between competencies and goals, objectives and results, in the form of performance in public positions (Zarifian, 2003; Bergue, 2014; Leme, 2005). These issues mobilize important changes in the organizational and managerial culture that privilege organizational strategies in patterns that strengthen the development of civil servants, bringing organizational and personal objectives closer together (Guimarães, 2000; Carbone et al., 2006), given that organizational and individual competencies must be intrinsically related (Mascarenhas, 2008).

In this context, Dalmau et al. (2022) suggest that it is appropriate to recognize practices developed by public administration entities, which can broaden the range of possibilities with an emphasis on feasibility and the challenges of implementation through successful experiences. For example, constant training based on the concept of transversal competencies and an organizational environment conducive to identifying and promoting internal corporate leadership are essential for the development of Brazil's federal civil servants in the quest to improve the quality of public management in institutions and to provide services with excellence for society (O'hara, Oliveira, Siqueira, Almeida Bizarria & Sampaio, 2023).

In this sense, the research problem is: What are the policies and practices aimed at developing civil servants in Brazilian federal universities? The goal is to broaden our understanding of the policies and practices aimed at developing civil servants within universities, considering the reference to Federal Decree n.º 5.707, of 2006, and Federal Decree n.º 9.991, of 2019, amended by Federal Decree n.º 10.506, of 2020, based on their People Development Plans. To this end, a thematic analysis of 23 plans was carried out in search of considerations in the sense of Competence Management, justifying the effort to support the process of drafting and implementing these instruments based on practical and theoretical inferences based on Competence Management.

2. Competence-based management in the context of personnel development in the Federal Executive

The field of people management is made up of various subsystems (recruitment, selection, indicators, targets, competency-based development, appraisals, positions and salaries) that are integrated and influence the Competency-Based Management (CBM) model (Lima; Lima, 2013).

In this context, competency-based management, or Competency Management, is characterized as a still recent management model, in the view of Sousa and Barbosa (2018), with greater representation and consolidation in the private sector or in public or mixed-capital companies, with greater progress in the public sector since 2006, although still in the implementation phase (Sousa & Barbosa, 2018).

Andrade and Ckagnazaroff (2018) understand that Competency-Based Management models have been widely disseminated over the last 20 years, which raises debates related to the public sector, since experiences in different countries, as recognized in OECD documents, demonstrate the inapplicability of universal models for this sector. Ubeda and Santos (2008) corroborate this idea, given that public organizations are still unable to apply the goals and results subsystem, which is one of the constituent elements of Competency-Based Management (Montezano et al., 2019).

In Brazil, considering the Brazilian government's emphasis since 2006, it can be recognized that public policies on the subject are still recent and generally in the implementation phase. In this sense, Nicolazzi (2013) understands that Le Boterf's (2006) approach, from the perspective of competences in the context of professional situations, in combination of organizational and individual competences, is more representative in the Brazilian public service.

Kriiger, Andrade, Silva, Mourão, Pizzol and Lima (2018), when referring to the report prepared in 2010 by the OECD, note that, in Brazil, Competency-Based Management is a relevant tool from the perspective of integration between various organizational units in favor of strategic priorities and objectives. To this end, the authors suggest that attention should be paid to the process of administrative discontinuity and the need to support organizational managers, with awareness-raising being a fundamental step in making the process a collective construction.

Federal Decree n.º 5.707, of February 23, 2006, defined the policy and Guidelines for Personnel Development, contemplating a medium and long-term vision, within the scope of careers and professional life (Bergue, 2020). The concept of 'competencies', adopted as a management tool for the development of federal civil servants (Brasil, 2006), emphasized "(i) improving the efficiency, effectiveness and quality of public services provided to citizens; (ii) permanent development of civil servants; (iii) adapting the competencies required of civil servants to the objectives of the institutions, with reference to the multiannual plan; (iv) dissemination and management of training actions; and (v) rationalization and effectiveness of spending on training" (Federal Decree 5.707, 2006). This implies taking on innovative and flexible processes to respond to social demands, while respecting the principles of public administration (Guimarães, 2000; Amaral, 2006; Silva, Cavalcante, Silva & Silva, 2021).

Dalmau et al. (2022) point out that after 15 years of Federal Decree n.º 5.707, a normative change related to the subject was introduced on August 28, 2019, through Federal Decree n.º 9.991, amended by Federal Decree n.º 10.506, of October 2, 2020, which institutes the National People Development Policy (PNDP). With the update, it is stated that the aim is to regulate and restructure the instruments, methods and procedures relating to the development of civil servants, with an emphasis on the competencies required for excellence in the service provided to citizens.

Thus, competency-based management needs to consider new concepts, as suggested by López (2005) and Brandão et al. (2008), with a view to drawing up indicators and targets, including mission and vision, as well as identifying existing competencies that are necessary for the organization's strategic objectives and monitoring (Carvalho et al., 2009). This movement cooperates with the Brazilian public administration's efforts to professionalize and modernize public services to improve the services offered to society (Carvalho et al., 2009). As a result, the diagnosis of competencies places greater emphasis on competencies that enable people to work in a context of change.

In the context of the universities, the People Development Plan is a medium-term strategic planning tool that mobilizes competencies, including a survey of the gap between existing competencies and those needed by the institution. The plans promotes actions, goals and evaluations based on policies inspired by the CBM, in line with Federal Decrees 9.991/2019 and 10.506/2020 (Brasil, 2019). In this way, the plans represents documents that embody practices and policies related to CBM in the universities, and therefore constitute the corpus of this study.

3. Methodology

As for the approach, this research is qualitative, based on the assumption that the world can be better understood from the context that integrates it (Godoy, 1995). As for the objectives, the research is descriptive, as it aims to describe the characteristics of the People Development Plans of Brazilian Federal Universities, drawing insights from these characteristics in the direction of competency-based management.

Initially, a search on the Ministry of Education's e-MEC website, using an advanced search with the filters 'Higher Education Institutions', 'Federal Public' and 'University', identified the universe of the study as being made up of 68 universities. Next, a manual survey of each university's 2022 plans was carried out by searching their institutional websites. To do this, the keywords 'people development plan' and 'people development' were used.

After that, only documents that were in line with Federal Decree n.º 9.991/2019, which provides for the National People Development Policy of the Federal, Autarchic and Foundational Public Administration, were selected. Only documents that referenced the Competency-Based Management model or had the word 'competency' in the text, in the singular or plural, adjectivized or not, were selected. The searches ended on July 21, 2022, and generated 23 results, which constitute the corpus of this documentary research. These 23 documents constituted the base for our analysis.

The data was processed within the parameters of Minayo's (2014) thematic analysis. The effort was divided into three phases: in the pre-analysis, the researchers carried out a floating reading of the selected plan to familiarize themselves with the format and content presented in the plans, so as to infer whether

the previously outlined objective and the chosen methodology would be suitable for carrying out the study. The researchers also used floating reading to confirm the constitution of the corpus, eliminating the risk of references to Competence Management or the word 'competence' being isolated and detached from Federal Decree 9.991/2019. The pre-analysis confirmed that the corpus consisted of 23 documents.

In the second stage, exploration of the material (Minayo, 2014), the authors described the plans by summarizing their contents, using the universities as context units. This resulted in Table 1. The synthesis work aimed to reach the core of understanding of the texts of the plans, considering their closeness or distance from the premises of Competence Management. In the material exploration phase, the categories dissected in the final stage were extracted.

Table 1. People Development Plans – Federal Universities in Brazil

Universities	Practices (Actions for People Development, linked to Policies/Programs/Projects)
UNIVASF	Actions: Assessment of needs, selection of demands with higher priorities, internal registration of instructors. Planned actions: Public area courses (Initiation, Bidding, Planning, Administrative Process, Communication, Conflicts), Courses: Retirement, Libras, Office, NR10, Chemical Waste, Statistics, Quantitative Methods, Marketing, Entrepreneurship, Sucupira, Digital Media, Heteroidentification and Racism; Workshops, Meetings, Discussion Groups; Trainings; Congresses, Seminars; Formal Education: Undergraduate; Specialization; Master's; Doctorate and Post-Doctorate.
UTFPR	Planned actions: Courses: ASD and Psychologist in Higher Education, Mental and Institutional Health, Text preparation and review, Drawings, Education of the deaf, Sign language interpreters, Solid waste, Book editor, Racism, Teamwork, Public policy service network, Ethics, Communication, Inclusive Education, Congresses, Immersion of partner universities, Law seminars, Postgraduate studies, Conferences and Assessments.
UNILA	Actions: preparation of the PNP, needs assessment. Planned actions: Management courses: Risks, Competencies, Ombudsman, Ethics, Emotions, Federal Bodies, Public Processes, among others. Courses in various areas: Leadership, Electronic Systems, Statistics, Good Practices, Pandemic, Planning, Data Science, Design, Drawing, Scrum, Law, Security, Finance, Logistics, Public Administration (contracting, evaluation, legislation, inspection) and Formal Education: Specialization in Tax Law and Certifications.
UFU	Actions: preparation of the plan, assessment of needs, referral of possible actions to the Training Division and questionnaires. Planned actions: Management courses (Ethics, leadership, projects, active methodologies, finance, administrative routines, communication), Public sector courses (Rights and duties, harassment, contracts, security, first aid, purchases, government prices), Academic courses (academic records, pedagogical practices, writing, electronic systems, ABNT, digital content, Prezzi and Office), Languages (Portuguese, French, Libras) and Seminars.
UNB	Actions: needs assessment with questionnaires, analysis and categorization, action schedule, presentation of the PNP to senior management. Planned actions: Quantitative methods, Project management, Conflict management, Violence at work, Telework performance, CMS Joomla 3.X, Public Area (Setting, Documents, Economy, Purchasing, Prices, Planning), Scientific Methodology, Research Project, Management reports, EAD Content, University Management, Office 365, Use of SEI, SIGRH, SIG UNB, UNB Languages, UNB Service.
UFSM	Actions: needs assessment with questionnaire, analysis, goals and internal actions. Planned actions: International and organizational development, Course Management Track, Assessments; Management courses (communication, leadership, risks, processes, planning, administration), Public sector courses (tenders, service, hiring, security, career) Academic area courses (academic systems, pedagogical practices, inclusion), Libras, Excel and Formal Education: Technical; Undergraduate; Specialization; Master's; Doctorate; Post-doctorate; Lectures, Civil Service Week, Integration Meetings.
UNITE	Planned actions: Courses: Hygiene and Expertise, Environmental Education, Data Analysis, Foreign Language, Teaching Techniques, Preparation for Public Examinations, Public Administration, E-social, Sustainability, Information Architecture, Contracting, ABNT, Document Management, Knowledge Management, Contracts, Accounting Statements, Risk Management, Bidding, among others. Congresses, Research Projects, Lectures, Workshops, Seminars, Symposiums, Forums, Conferences, Udemy and Alura, Annual Meeting, Internships, Extension, Formal Education: Postgraduate, Master's, Doctorate and Postdoctorate.
UFSC	Actions: needs assessment with online form, absences, dialogue, data analysis and creation of indicators, analysis of assessments and suggestions, submission to SIPEC, consolidation of data and identification of cross-cutting actions. Planned actions: Courses, seminars, symposiums, conferences, congresses, meetings, workshops, lectures, specialization, master's, doctorate, post-doctorate, among others. Actions offered by formal education systems, in public or private institutions, at different levels of education. Note: the file does not have a list of planned actions, only the needs.
UFS	Actions: needs assessment, creation of the plan in table format, listing the items involved (cost, target audience, need, course modality, Unit, thematic area). Note: The file does not have information on planned actions, only the needs found.
UFRN	Actions: needs assessment in SIGRH and Google Forms, absences and licenses, data analysis to create actions. Planned actions: Courses in the management area (waste, communication, sustainability, social responsibility, conflicts, ethics, emotions, planning), Courses in the public area (career, contracts, governance, data protection), Languages (Libras, French, English, Spanish and German), Academic area courses (Tutoring, public speaking, hybrid learning, integrated systems, test platform, learning difficulties), Server Month, Virtual Table and Seminars.
UFRJ	Actions: needs assessment, creation of the development plan, listing the items involved (cost, target audience, need, type of action, workload, thematic area). Note: The file does not have information on planned actions, only the needs identified.

UFRGS	Actions: needs assessment with consultations at the units and analysis of the history of the most frequent courses, filling in data in SIPEC and forwarding, indicating needs; ENAP identifies the transversal needs, suggests available courses and diagnoses new courses; and the institution cross-references the approved needs with the skills gap. Planned actions: Courses, training, workshops, seminars, lectures, forums, EVG courses, ENAP courses, courses not covered by EDUFRGS, ENAP and EVG and Formal Education.
UFDPAr	Actions: needs assessment, creation of the plan report, relating need, theme, subtheme, associated competence, information, target audience, unit, structuring system of the federal executive branch, whether the action will be free, expected cost, whether the need can be met by the government's own school, the state and public agents). Note: the file does not have information on planned actions, only the needs.
UFMS	Actions: needs assessment, based on 2021 actions, number of employees, need for development, management activities and improvement, aligned with the UFMS PDI 2020-2024. Courses are classified according to the Type of Learning (initiation to public service, general training, management training and interrelationship between environments). Courses: Entrepreneurship; English, Spanish, Libras; Ethics; Excel; Teacher training in higher education; Pedagogical training; Process mapping, Specialization, Master's, Doctorate, among others.
UFMG	Actions: assessment of needs, analysis and systematization, recording of data in SIPEC. Submission of the plan for analysis and manifestation of SIPEC, whose feedback was assessed by the DDP. Planned actions: Courses in the management area (processes, performance, conflicts, good practices, leadership, organization, assets), Courses in the public area (tenders, contracts, purchases), Inclusion, University Extension, Excel, Pedagogical practices, Accessibility, Remote and Hybrid Teaching, Conversations in PRORH, Reception of new and recently hired teachers, Formal Education: Specialization, Master's and Doctorate.
UFFS	Actions: needs assessment; development of development actions. Preparation of guidelines for requesting execution and/or participation in a training event, including in a flow format; delimitation of responsibilities for those involved (DCAP; requesting area and participating server); Note: the document contains needs, but not planned actions. It is up to the server/organizational unit to define and request them.
UFF	Actions: diagnosis of demands and preparation of projects for actions. Planned actions: in-person, hybrid and distance learning courses and workshops for technical improvement, formal education, management and initiation into public service. Ex: analysis and improvement of processes; support for training initiatives, service to the public with special needs; disciplinary administrative process; qualification assistance program; governance; initiation of public service at UFF.
UFCSPA	Actions: creation of a spreadsheet based on the need for the theme, associated competence, target audience, unit, title, workload, completion, cost, and area. Planned actions: Amerek /UFMG; Advanced SINAPI; Neuroscience; Bioethics, Specialization in Digital Health; Post- doctoral internship in the USA with support from a public notice; post-doctorate around maternal and child health; teaching in digital education; Brazilian congress of speech therapy, among others.
UFBA	Actions: individual questionnaire; validation of needs, consolidation of responses and registration in Sipec ; opening of the process in SEI for approval by the Vice-Rector of Human Resources Management; forwarding of the process for approval in Sipec and via dispatch in the SEI process; includes the submission protocol in the process and awaits Sipec 's response ; opening of the plan monitoring processes informing the offers of government schools to each Vice-Rector's Office for inclusion of the certificates that will be used in the 2022 plan execution report . Note: the file does not have the list of planned actions.
UFAM	Planned actions: Leave, training and qualifications; leave for postgraduate studies; short-term actions (internal and external). There are actions planned in a separate calendar, for example: Preparation of institutional performance indicators; Management of strategy in BSC; Personnel management - basis of leadership; conflict resolution and negotiation, among others. Note: the calendar is updated periodically. Some courses are no longer included in the available calendar.
UFAL	Actions: application of the FNLC; analysis of regulations; alignment of actions with institutional objectives; implementation of risk management; forwarding of the plan, approval; implementation and execution. Planned actions: Courses: Contracts; Use of ICTs, Legislation and academic standards; Libras; Equipment tenders; Accessibility standards; Risk management; Python; Public procurement; JBI scope review; Knowledge management in the public sector; Video classes, Excel, Innovative/hybrid classes; Human rights of children and adolescents; Management control; Educational technologies; Multimedia production; Academic and university management; Process management; Public budget and procurement processes, National Meetings, among others.
UFABC	The plan indicates: Need/ Data Supporting the Need/ Consolidated/ Theme/ Subtheme / Other Themes or Subthemes Not Listed/ Associated Competence/ Cross-Cutting Need/ Non-cross-cutting/ Target Audience/ Unit(s)/ Structuring System of the Federal Executive Branch/ Type of Learning/ Subtype (specification) of Learning/ Modality/ Expected Title of the Development Action/ Expected Workload/ Expected End/ Free Action/ Expected Cost/ Need Can Be Met by Own Government School/ Other Information States/ Public Agents/.
UFES	The document has a total of 136 pages. The actions are separated into courses, formal education, other unspecified types, practical experience, events, among others. Examples of actions: Relational intelligence; Master's degree in Communication; Team management and leadership in public service; Google Workspace; Post-doctorate; Master's degree; Digital technologies; Doctorate; Innovation and digital transformation; New spelling agreement; Scheduled study in the area of Psychology - Training license in the form of scheduled studies on the proposed topic, among others.

Source: own elaboration.

In the third and final stage, the interpretative effort based on the reference literature, the authors analyzed the plans, considering the premises incorporated into Federal Decree n. ° 9.991/2019 and Competency-Based Management, through the following categories of analysis: (i) diversity and creativity, (ii) focus on skills, not competencies, (iii) plans, goals and results, (iv) the role of people management units in the public sector and (v) difficulties in analyzing the plans and best practices.

4. Brazilian Federal Universities and People Development Plans

According to the MEC (2024), the Brazilian Federal Universities are fundamental institutions for the country's higher education system, offering free, quality education. They are fundamental to research, innovation and the training of professionals in various areas of knowledge. With a presence in all Brazilian regions, they promote social inclusion and regional socio-economic development. In addition, their administrative and academic autonomy allows them to implement programs and policies tailored to local and national needs. To guarantee academic and administrative excellence, its People Development Plans aim to train and develop teaching and technical-administrative staff, promoting continuous qualification through training programs, refresher courses and postgraduate courses. This contributes to the improvement of educational services and innovation in educational and management practices within universities.

4.1. People Development Plans for Brazilian Federal Universities: A Descriptive Overview

According to table 1, it can be seen that Federal Public Universities have prioritized the survey of needs using virtual tools, whether through e-mails (UFFS), forms (UFS) or questionnaires (UFU). There are also experiences on cloud, in which the institution has prepared a spreadsheet available to be filled in by different sectors at the same time, on an electronic site, with automatic saving (UFAM and UFRJ). On the other hand, there are HEIs that opt for the methodology of cross-checking data, mapping the frequency of courses and the demands of the units (UFSC).

There is also evidence of the prominence of events. There is a prevalence of courses, seminars, symposiums, conferences, congresses, meetings, workshops, lectures, and other forms of training, given in person, online or in hybrid form. These events add to people's development as they allow information to be exchanged between intra- and interorganizational players.

Another constant in the plans is the inclusion of formal qualifications, with lato and stricto sensu postgraduate programs aimed at teachers and technical-administrative staff. It should also be noted that there is a postgraduate program specifically for people management based on competencies offered by UFBA, whose main target audience is public managers. It should also be noted that the events and training that make up the plans are centered on more than one dimension of competence, which is also in line with the idea of transversal competences, established by Federal Decree n. ° 9.991/2019. There are events and training courses that focus on technical, administrative, psychosocial and political dimensions, with topics that cover efficiency and effectiveness combined with social responsibility.

Efficiency and effectiveness are manifested in events and training courses involving data science (UFU), statistics (UFMG), research methodology (UNB), marketing and communication (UFPI/UFDPAR). Social responsibility, meanwhile, is present in those courses that engender debates on violence (UNILA), women (UFSCPA), sustainability (UFU), inclusion (UFMS), accessibility (UFRN) and ethics and bioethics (UFAL). It can also be said that the training courses have moved towards discussing the trajectory of teachers and technical-administrative staff, with discussions about their careers and routines, with the aim of combining time and productivity with professional progress.

The HEIs have also taken care to provide different types of learning for their staff, even in terms of the stage of their career they are at. Some HEIs offer introductory courses in public service (UNILA), while others strive to turn their civil servants into public university managers (UFRJ). These courses are aimed at teaching and technical-administrative staff, which broadens the interrelationships between the different organizational environments, allowing for technical improvement and the integration of different knowledge and skills.

The Covid-19 pandemic also had an impact on the preparation of the plans for the year under review, requiring the expansion of courses on topics related to governance and risk management (see the UFRGS PLAN). This is in line with the scenario of uncertainties caused by the pandemic event, which demanded a rapid restructuring of the middle and end activities of higher education institutions, including the adoption of 'new' methodologies to comply with the undergraduate and postgraduate calendars.

Some of the country's leading HEIs stand out for offering a wide variety of events and training courses, which other HEIs end up joining if they are available. It is believed that this movement engenders, at the same time, a response to development needs, savings in public resources, and integration between professionals with different skills. Furthermore, the interaction between HEIs from different regions of the country allows for a broader debate on Brazilian reality from different socio-economic perspectives, enabling contextualized and critical actions in the sphere of administrative and educational performance.

On another front, all the events and training offered by the Higher Education Institutions and the Schools of Government have ended up forming a 'Portfolio of Development Actions', which is made available to internal and external demand. This Portfolio allows teachers and technical-administrative staff to have their development needs met, *pari passu* with the achievement of promotions and progressions in their careers, giving a more dynamic perspective to their careers in the public bureaucracy.

It should also be noted that different HEIs have different training priorities. UFTPR has an emphasis on legal content; UFRN, on content focused on mediation and tutoring; UNIR, on content focused on formal education and UFMS on content focused on administrative routine. This reinforces the idea that each HEI faces its own challenges, requiring specific actions to overcome them.

These differences between the HEIs are not only around training content. The plans themselves have different formats and were drawn up using different techniques. While some needs assessments were carried out via e-mail, others were done using forms or a cloud. Some institutions chose to hold events to make their

staff aware of the importance of the PLAN (UNIVASF, UFBA, UFSC, among others), while others did not do so or did not report having done so.

Some plans provide definitions for the concepts they use - such as competencies or transversal competencies. UNIVASF's PLAN is noteworthy, as it has a specific section called 'The Concepts That Permeate the 2022 PLAN'. However, many other plans do not go into the subject in depth. Some plans cite, by name, each of the norms on which they are based, making references to laws and decrees, as well as to the HEI's Institutional Development Plan (UFMS, UFF, UNB, UFSC, etc.). Others, however, do not.

There are also major differences in the format of the plan's final document. Some institutions present it in spreadsheet format, in PDF or XLSX, without much detail on the process of implementation. Others present it in a more elaborate form, through booklets and/or manuals, which set out the main stages in the preparation of the PLAN, along with the actions taken in each of them by the various sectors involved in the construction of the Plan. On its website, UFBA has a Guide to Drawing Up a People Development Plan, produced by the Ministry of the Economy.

Some of the more elaborate plans also have data visualization tools, such as figures, graphs and tables (see the one from UFSC), which make it easier to understand the step-by-step process of editing the Plan.

4.2. People Development Plans at Brazilian Federal Universities: Insights from Theory and Practice

4.2.1. Diversity and creativity in the process of drawing up and implementing plans

Understanding that competency-based management is a model in the process of maturing and consolidating in Brazilian public organizations, which are evolving towards mapping competencies and ways to develop them (Favorini, Silva & Crepaldi, 2014; Kreisig et al., 2021; Tamada & Cunha, 2022), allows us to understand that the process that constitutes its application is dynamic and, above all, adaptable, given the current references of public administration (Garcia, 2013).

Initially, the variety of processes used by the universities to apply Federal Decree n.º 9.9991/2019 sounds connected to the reality of new public management - which is increasingly moving towards the adoption of standard operating procedures in line with activities carried out in the private sector. A more diligent look, however, leads to comprehensive understandings of the plans analyzed and their consequences.

The fact is that, more than 15 years after Federal Decree 5.707/2006, the universities have not adopted a uniform process for drawing up and implementing their plans, so these documents come in different forms (spreadsheets, documents) and formats (.xlxs, .doc, .pdf), with different contents, which interact to a greater or lesser extent with the guidelines of SGP-ENAP/SEDGG/ME Normative Instruction 21, of February 1, 2021 (Queiroz, 2022). If, on the one hand, this factor makes it difficult to interpret some Plans, on the other hand, it announces the diversity of contexts, challenges and perspectives that the universities face in consolidating them (Santos, 2018; Queiroz, 2022).

It should be noted that the process of developing competencies takes place in a contextualized way and is directly linked to the process of drawing up and implementing plans. If the acquisition of skills depends on factors that permeate the activities carried out in the work context, including individual and collective characteristics and dispositions, communication, physical structure and the role of the manager, among others (Lima & Silva, 2015), it is reasonable that the plans are also influenced by these factors.

Thus, the results suggest that the diversity of present in the plans is directly proportional to the diversity of social, economic, cultural and financial contexts in which the universities are inserted, organizations built collectively, in an environment that leads to disputes over experiences and discourses (Silva & Ribeiro, 2022). These diversities give rise to reflections on the permeability of the plans to the context, since these documents present the institutional, technical and political priorities of the institutions.

The tension between different contexts, however, does not eliminate the process of institutional isomorphism, understood from a coercive perspective, regarding DiMaggio and Powell (2005), in this case made possible by federal regulations (5.707/2009, 9.991/2019, 21/2021, etc.) and by SIPEC's own actions. In the plans analyzed, for example, there is a strong focus on handling systems and programs, which indicates an increasingly computerized organizational political arrangement in the universities (Fonseca & Meneses, 2016).

The issues of isomorphism and diversity are marginally related to discussions about organizational creativity. Comprehensive legislation (policy) allows for the adoption of different strategies to achieve the same end, which provokes reflections from those involved in the process - what to do and how to do it to achieve the best cost-benefit result? These reflections give rise to new ideas, processes, products and services (Dória et al., 2017), always mediated by Normative Instruction 21/2021. As it is an indispensable tool in a dynamic and unstable scenario, organizational creativity must be encouraged, without prejudice to compliance with the relevant legislation.

With this in mind, some universities have, over the years, put together best practices in the construction of their plans. Some even release complete documents of their Plans, which allow for a clearer reading of the activities carried out during the year following the PLAN. These actions should be seen as good practice and disseminated to other institutions as a way of improving their preparation and execution processes.

In this sense, good practices mean plans that are prepared and executed in a well-founded manner, with well-defined stages that include diagnosing competencies, carrying out actions and monitoring risks and results, with a view to the effectiveness of the GPC and good use of public money (Queiroz, 2022). The effort

must also be extended to SIPEC, the body that, in addition to technically evaluating the reports submitted, must provide feedback to guide the subsequent planning and execution stages.

4.2.2. Focus on skills, not competencies

The myriads of actions provided for in the plans are part of a model that aims to reach both middle and end areas, including administrative staff and teachers. The activities involve courses and events, including specializations, master's degrees, and doctorates as internal training. The diversity of actions planned suggests that staff from all areas of the universities will be covered to the extent of their institutional duties in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes.

However, in the Plans, this relationship between institutional needs and attributions is not always evident, which hinders analysis of the results expected from courses and events, fragmenting the link between the PLAN, a strategic planning instrument, and CBM (Albuquerque, Masaro & Almeida, 2021). In reality, the results suggest that the model's focus is on training rather than competencies, which points to a break between the Plans and their assumptions based on CBM.

This scenario seems to be related to the problem of the disruption of accumulated knowledge within the federal public administration, as pointed out by Kriiger et al. (2018), which hinders the collection, organization, sharing and analysis of the body of knowledge that impacts the pursuit of organizational objectives - a point that becomes neuralgic from the perspective of CBM.

Federal Decree n.º 9.991/2019 itself does not require universities to specify the relationship between training and competencies, but only to present the development needs and the actions planned to meet them. Article 8 of Normative Instruction SGP-ENAP/SEDGG/ME No. 21/2021 requires a breakdown of the competencies associated with development needs, but the results indicate that not all plans are aligned with this requirement - it can be seen that, out of a universe of 68 universities, only 23 presented plans in accordance with the premises of Federal Decree n.º 9.991/2019. Furthermore, Albuquerque, Massaro and Almeida (2021) point out that, despite the Federal Decree, not all Brazilian federal public universities use or intend to use CBM.

4.2.3. Plans, targets and results

One aspect worth highlighting is that the plans analyzed do not mention mechanisms for measuring goals or results related to training, which undermines the binding force of the actions taken, making the process of developing competencies unmeasurable. The absence of goals and results related to the plan is not a particular issue for the universities and permeates the application of the CBM model in public organizations (Ubeda & Santos, 2008), despite being, in theory, one of its constituent elements (Montezano et al., 2019).

The fact is that targets and results refer to evaluation processes, which require specific regulation in the public sector, in accordance with the principle of legality. There are also issues inherent in the implementation of these processes, which are mediated by the organizational culture and the organizational climate, including resistance (Marques et al., 2014).

If, on the one hand, targets and results refer to evaluation, generating resistance, on the other hand, they ratify the importance of the GPC model, informing the target audience that competencies play a leading role within the organization, generating 'rewards' from accumulated knowledge, skills and attitude (and manifested in day-to-day work).

4.2.4. The role of people management units in the public sector

People management units are made up of subsystems that, in an integrated way, carry out their institutional duties, influencing the competency-based management model and the PLAN (Lima & Lima, 2013). The challenge facing these units is to balance the bill for applying a model developed for the private sector to the public sector.

The recruitment and selection, training and development, appraisal and remuneration, or positions and salaries subsystems need to deal with the reality of the public service, which has its own particularities when it comes into contact with CBM. The way of entering the public sector is one of them, since the tests and titles generally disregard skills and attitudes, focusing only on technical knowledge (Montezano et al., 2019).

In addition, the training and development of people is hampered by the lack of incentives for training, which is related to the remuneration structure that is not always linked to this aspect. As a result, civil servants may be discouraged from taking part in courses and events aimed at developing their skills (Dutra, Zuppani & Nascimento, 2016).

These factors intersect in the process of drawing up and implementing the PLAN, a document directly related to the organization's individual and collective competencies, dictating the impact that the document will have on the organizational reality and the development of the profile of civil servants (Queiroz, 2022).

In this sense, the study suggests that the efficiency factors of a plans are before its preparation and permeate cultural and normative issues pertaining to the public sector. In this field, it is up to the people management unit to deal with the challenges through negotiation processes with senior management and civil servants, so that the training provided for in the plan, based on CBM premises, has the expected effect in terms of gains for the institution, linked to the social relevance of its purpose, a move that requires technical and political strengthening of these units.

4.2.5. Difficulties in analyzing plans and best practices

The variety of processes used to draw up and implement the plans make it difficult to analyze the data contained in the plans. The lack of uniformity in the elements required the researchers to try to understand and synthesize the findings, which, however, does not fully reflect the diversity of constructions found. The variety also made it difficult to compare the plans drawn up by different universities, which raises doubts about the level of exchange of experiences and communication between the institutions. However, this did not hinder the identification of 'best practices' linked to these plans.

The definition of concepts used in the plan, reference to the standards on which it was based, and the construction of data visualization elements (graphs, tables, and images) are some examples. It can also be seen that some universities are moving towards the development of booklets and manuals on the plan, detailing the importance of the plans, the stages of preparation and execution, and the sectors responsible.

Publicizing the Plans through booklets helps sectors not directly involved in the process to understand their importance, helping with what authors call 'sensitization' to CBM (Silva & Trevisol, 2019), which is, in short, a phase of preparation for the application of the model, making civil servants aware of its importance and relevance.

5. Considerations in the direction of competency-based management

In order to understand the policies and practices aimed at the development of civil servants within universities, considering the reference to Federal Decree n.º 5.707 of 2006 and Federal Decree n.º 9.991 of 2019, amended by Federal Decree n.º 10.506 of 2020, a manual survey of the 2022 plans published on their institutional websites was carried out. In this sense, it was perceived that there is evidence of diversity and creativity, with influence on the format and content of the documents, considering the contextual varieties in which the universities are inserted, as well as the legal, institutional and individual provisions of those involved in this process of drafting and implementing the aforementioned plans analyzed in the research.

There is also evidence of difficulties in identifying the link between the training proposed in the plans and the competencies related to the positions and duties of the employees of the universities, which fragments the understanding that the Plans are strategic planning instruments. The model suggests that the focus of the plans remain on providing training, rather than on developing the competencies needed for the institutional objectives.

It was also concluded that it is difficult to establish metrics related to the plans, with a view to measuring the results of the actions carried out within the scope of the plans. The lack of evaluation processes makes it difficult to measure the efficiency of the plans, while at the same time contradicting the premises of the Competency-Based Management model.

From the research, discussions emerge about the role of the people management units of the universities, which mediate technical and political criteria in the implementation of the plan, given that their actions permeate management issues linked to organizational culture. Strengthening these units emerges as an agenda for achieving the objectives set out in Federal Decree 5.707/2006 and 9.991/2019.

Despite the contextual difficulties, several universities have moved to implement better plans in line with the dictates of the New Public Administration, using information technology and data visualization tools to highlight the relevance and importance of plans and, above all, competencies. In this sense, the role of SIPEC, with its feedback and monitoring of the plans, and ENAP, which helps coordinate training, can be overlooked.

This research is limited by the quantity, form and content of the plans selected, which makes it difficult to synthesize the data. To continue the study, it is suggested that multiple case studies be carried out to identify the details that permeate the technical and political construction of a People Development Plan in Federal Public Universities, with a focus on the processes of institutional isomorphism and cultural resistance to the use of metrics and evaluations within the scope of the plan.

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